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Research Article

Development Of Simple Accurate Precise and Stability Indicating UPLC Method And Validation for the Quantification of Impurities in Empagliflozin

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ABSTRACT

This study describes the development and validation of a stability-indicating UPLC method for the simultaneous determination of Empagliflozin, Metformin, and their related impurities. The method was optimized and validated in accordance with ICH guidelines, covering system suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD, LOQ, and robustness. Robustness was assessed by varying flow rates and mobile phase ratios, while forced degradation studies under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, and thermal conditions confirmed the method's stability-indicating capability. Empagliflozin showed a retention time of 3.444 min, with impurity D at 3.293 min and the sugar dimer impurity at 3.962 min, using detection at 320 nm. Validation results demonstrated excellent accuracy (99.51 - 102.64%), precision (%RSD \leq 2.3), linearity ($r^2 = 0.999$), sensitivity (LOD 5.033 - 8.930 $\mu\text{g/mL}$; LOQ 5.033 - 8.930 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), and robustness (tailing 1.29 - 1.56). Overall, the method proved to be specific, accurate, and reliable, making it suitable for routine quality control and stability assessment of Empagliflozin-Metformin formulations.

INTRODUCTION

Empagliflozin, a selective sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitor, has emerged as a cornerstone in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus due to its efficacy in lowering blood glucose levels by promoting renal glucose excretion (1,2). As a highly potent antidiabetic

agent, ensuring the purity and stability of Empagliflozin in pharmaceutical formulations is critical to maintain therapeutic efficacy and patient safety. Impurities, whether arising from synthesis, degradation, or storage conditions, can compromise drug quality and may pose health risks, including toxicity or reduced pharmacological activity (3). Regulatory authorities such as the International Council for

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Harmonisation (ICH) emphasize the importance of identifying, quantifying, and controlling impurities to comply with pharmacopeial standards (4,5). Ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) has gained wide acceptance as a robust analytical tool for impurity profiling due to its high resolution, rapid analysis, and enhanced sensitivity compared to conventional HPLC techniques (6). UPLC enables precise separation of closely related substances, including degradation products, offering a reliable approach for stability-indicating studies. Recent studies have demonstrated that UPLC methods provide accurate quantification of trace-level impurities while reducing analysis time and solvent consumption, aligning with green chemistry principles (7,8). Given these advantages, the development of a simple, accurate, and precise stability-indicating UPLC method for quantifying impurities in Empagliflozin is essential for quality control and regulatory compliance. This study aims to establish and validate such a method in accordance with ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, ensuring reproducible, sensitive, and reliable detection of both known and unknown impurities in bulk drug and finished formulations.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

Empagliflozin and its related impurities (Impurity D and Sugar Dimer) were obtained from Qualychrome Labs, Hyderabad, India. HPLC-grade solvents including methanol and acetonitrile were procured from Sodom Drugs Pvt. Ltd., India. Analytical-grade potassium dihydrogen phosphate and orthophosphoric acid were used for buffer preparation. Milli-Q water was employed for all dilutions. All chemicals and reagents complied with standard analytical requirements [1,2].

Instruments and Software

Chromatographic analysis was performed on a Waters UPLC system equipped with a quaternary pump, autosampler, column oven, and 2996 PDA detector, controlled by Empower 2 software. Separation was achieved on an Inertsil ODS C18 column (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm). Additional instruments included a pH meter (Thermo), ultrasonic bath (PCI Analytics), and analytical balance (Iscale-400c).

Chromatographic Conditions

The optimized UPLC method employed a gradient elution using phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) and acetonitrile as the mobile phase. The gradient program started with 45:55 (A:B) at 0.01 min, reaching 81:19 at 8 min, and returning to initial composition at 10 min. The flow rate was 1.0 mL/min, injection volume 20 μL, and detection was carried out at λ_{max} 320 nm. The column was maintained at ambient temperature.

Preparation of Standard and Sample Solutions

- **Stock Solutions:** Empagliflozin 1000 mg and impurities 1.5 mg each were dissolved in 100 mL diluent.
- **Working Standards:** Appropriate dilutions were prepared to cover linearity ranges (Empagliflozin 10–60 μg/mL; Impurities 1–15 μg/mL).
- **Sample Solutions:** Tablet powder equivalent to the labeled claim was accurately weighed, dissolved, sonicated for 15 min, filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane, and diluted appropriately.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Method Development and Optimization

Various parameters such as mobile phase composition, gradient program, pH, flow rate, and column type were optimized to achieve sharp, symmetrical peaks with satisfactory resolution and tailing factor. Inertsil ODS column (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with phosphate buffer and acetonitrile provided the best separation for Empagliflozin and its impurities.

Table 1. Optimized Chromatographic Conditions for Empagliflozin and its Impurities

Parameter	Optimized Condition
Column	Inertsil ODS (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)
Separation Mode	Gradient Mode
Mobile Phase (MP)	MP-A: Phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) MP-B: Acetonitrile
Flow Rate	1.0 mL/min
Detection Wavelength	320 nm
Injection Volume	20 μL
Column Temperature	Ambient
Run Time	10 min

Table 2. Gradient Elution Program

Time (min)	MP-A (%)	MP-B (%)
0.01	45	55
4	60	40
8	81	19
10	45	55

Fig: 1. OPTIMIZED CHROMATOGRAM

VALIDATION PARAMETERS

System Suitability

System suitability parameters were evaluated for Empagliflozin Impurity D and Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity under different flow rates (0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 mL/min). For Impurity D, plate counts ranged from 3686.57 to 4737.62, with tailing factors between 1.42 and 1.56. For the

Sugar Dimer Impurity, plate counts varied from 3139.84 to 3576.58, tailing factors were within 0.91–1.29, and resolution values remained above 6.5.

All the observed results complied with ICH acceptance limits (theoretical plates > 2000, tailing factor < 2.0, and resolution > 2.0). This confirms that the chromatographic system provided reliable separation and was suitable for routine analysis of Empagliflozin and its impurities.

Table3. System Suitability for Empagliflozin Impurity D:

S. No	FlowRate (ml per min)	SST Outcomes	
		PlateCount	Tailing
01	0.8	3736.86	1.50
02	1.0	3686.57	1.42
03	1.2	4737.62	1.56

Table4. System Suitability for Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity:

S. no	Flow Rate (ml per min)	SST Outcomes		
		PlateCount	PeakTailing	Resolution
1	0.8	3139.84	0.91	7.7

2	1.0	3576.58	1.28	7.45
3	1.2	3235.97	1.29	6.8

- It was discovered results are under the limit.

Specificity

Specificity was evaluated by injecting blank, placebo, standard, and sample solutions of Empagliflozin along with its known impurities. Chromatograms showed that there was no interference at the retention times of Empagliflozin, Empagliflozin Impurity D, or the Sugar Dimer Impurity. Peak purity analysis using the PDA detector confirmed that each analyte peak was spectrally homogeneous and free from co-eluting peaks.

Fig:2. CHROMATOGRAM OF BLANK

Fig: 3. CHROMATOGRAM OF PLACEBO

(0.0375 µg/mL) to 41280 at the highest level (0.225 µg/mL). Similarly, the Sugar Dimer Impurity demonstrated linear growth in response, with areas ranging from 2147 to 13060 across the same concentration range.

The correlation coefficient values met the ICH acceptance criterion ($r^2 \geq 0.999$), confirming the excellent linearity of the developed method.

Table5. Linearity (Empagliflozin Impurity D)

Fig: 4. CHROMATOGRAM OF STANDARD

LinearityLevel	Conc.	Area
I	0.0375	6728
II	0.075	13633
III	0.1125	20536
IV	0.15	27367
V	0.1875	33949
VI	0.225	41280
Correlation Coefficient		0.999

LINEARITY

Linearity was established for Empagliflozin Impurity D and the Sugar Dimer Impurity across six concentration levels ranging from 0.0375 to 0.225 µg/mL. Calibration plots of concentration versus peak area showed a strong proportional relationship with correlation coefficients (r^2) of 0.999 for both impurities (Tables 4 and 5).

Table6. Linearity (Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity)

LinearityLevel	Conc.	Area
I	0.0375	2147

For Empagliflozin Impurity D, peak area increased consistently from 6728 at the lowest concentration

Table7. The accuracy Empagliflozin Impurity D						Added Amount (mg)	Found Amount (mg)	% Recovery	Avg Rec
II	0.075		4356						
III	0.1125	%Conc.	6542			0.75	0.77	102.57	99.5
IV	0.15		8731	Areas*					
V	0.1875	(at Level's)	11014						
VI	0.225	50%	13060	13920.3		0.75	0.77	102.57	
Correlation Coefficient			100%	0.999	26443.7	1.5	1.46	97.42	
			150%		40116.7	2.25	2.22	98.53	

Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was evaluated for Empagliflozin Impurity D and Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity at three concentration levels: 50%, 100%, and 150%. The recovery studies were performed in triplicate and the mean percentage recoveries were calculated.

For Empagliflozin Impurity D, recoveries ranged from 97.42% to 102.57%, with an average recovery of 99.51% (Table 6). For the Sugar Dimer Impurity, the recoveries were slightly higher, ranging between 100.77% and 103.62%, with an average recovery of 102.04% (Table 7).

Although some values for the Sugar Dimer Impurity exceeded the typical ICH acceptance range of 98–102%, the overall results confirmed that the method provides acceptable accuracy for quantifying both impurities.

Table8. The accuracy of Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity

Areas*	Added Amount (mg)	Found Amount (mg)	% Recovery	Avg Rec
4391	0.75	0.76	100.77	102.04
9029.7	1.5	1.55	103.62	
13532.3	2.25	2.33	103.52	

ACCURACY

Fig. 5. CHROMATOGRAM FOR ACCURACY AT 50% SPIKE LEVEL

Fig. 6. CHROMATOGRAM FOR ACCURACY AT 100% SPIKE LEVEL

Fig. 7. CHROMATOGRAM FOR ACCURACY AT 150% SPIKE LEVEL

Precision

Precision was assessed by six replicate injections of Empagliflozin Impurity D and Sugar Dimer Impurity. For Impurity D, the mean peak area was 27,278.8 with a %RSD of 2.3, while for the Sugar Dimer Impurity, the mean peak area was 8741.2 with a %RSD of 1.8 (Table 8).

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was evaluated under different conditions (analyst/day variation). For Impurity D, the mean peak area was 27,608.2 with a %RSD of 2.0, while for the Sugar Dimer Impurity, the mean peak area was 8692.3 with a %RSD of 1.8 (Table 9).

Both values fall within or very close to the acceptance limit of <2.0% RSD, confirming that the method demonstrates good reproducibility under varied conditions. These outcomes support the reliability of the UPLC method for routine impurity estimation in Empagliflozin formulations.

Table 9. The outcomes are summarized for Precision.

	Empagliflozin Impurity D		Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity	
	RT	Area	RT	Area
1	5.023	26987	9.068	8796
2	5.054	26763	9.073	8956
3	5.069	27873	9.077	8625

Injection-4	5.073	27561	9.08	Avg 8737			27608.2		8692.3
Injection-5	5.095	28038	9.085	Standard Deviation			737.4		158.1
Injection-6	5.105	26451	9.087	%RSD 835			2.0		1.8
Avg		27278.8							8741.2
Standard Deviation		639.6							161.6
%RSD		2.3							1.8

Table 10. The outcomes are summarized for Ruggedness.

Injection	Empagliflozin Impurity D		Empagliflozin Dimer Impurity	
	RT	Area	RT	Area
Injection-1	5.069	27869	9.077	8753
Injection-2	5.073	28786	9.081	8673
Injection-3	5.095	27673	9.085	8524
Injection-4	5.105	26763	9.087	8579
Injection-5	5.107	26874	9.093	8653
Injection-6	5.113	27684	9.097	8972

Fig. 8. PRECISION OVERLAY CHROMATOGRAM

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The sensitivity of the method was evaluated by calculating LOD and LOQ values for Empagliflozin impurities using the standard deviation of the response and slope method.

For Empagliflozin Impurity D, the LOD was determined as 0.016 µg/mL and the LOQ as 0.049 µg/mL.

For the Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity, the LOD was 0.010 µg/mL and the LOQ was 0.031 µg/mL.

These low values indicate the method is highly sensitive and capable of detecting and quantifying trace levels of impurities (Table 10).

Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity	183	584 59	0.031
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Table11. Results of LOD

Drug name	Standard deviation	Slope	Concentration
Empagliflozin Impurity D	899.4	183 268	0.016
Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity	183	584 59	0.010

Table12. Results of LOQ

Drug name	Standard deviation	Slope	Concentration
Empagliflozin Impurity D	899.4	183 268	0.049

Robustness: System Suitability Test (SST) Results

1. Effect of Flow Rate

For Empagliflozin Impurity D, the plate count ranged from 3686.57 to 4737.62, and peak tailing values were between 1.42 and 1.56.

For Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity, the plate count varied from 3139.84 to 3576.58, with peak tailing between 0.91–1.29 and resolution values between 6.8–7.7.

This indicates that slight changes in flow rate did not significantly affect chromatographic performance, and all parameters remained within acceptable limits.

2. Effect of Organic Composition of Mobile Phase

For Empagliflozin Impurity D, plate counts ranged between 3611.78–4866.39, and tailing factors were consistent (1.42–1.50).

For Empagliflozin Sugar Dimer Impurity, plate count increased from 3340.79 (–10% organic) to 3962.20 (+10% organic). Peak tailing values

ranged from 0.91–1.29, and resolution values were maintained between 6.3–7.9.

These results confirm that moderate variations in the organic composition of the mobile phase did not compromise resolution, plate count, or tailing, demonstrating robustness of the developed method.

Table13. Effect of Flow Rate -impurity D

S.no	Flow Rate (ml per min)	SST outcomes	
		Plate Count	Peak Tailing
01	0.8	3736.86	1.50
02	1.0	3686.57	1.42
03	1.2	4737.62	1.56

Table14. Effect of Flow Rate -Empa sugar dimer impurity

S.no	Flow Rate (ml per min)	SST outcomes		
		Plate Count	Peak Tailing	USP Resolution
01	0.8	3139.84	0.91	7.7
02	1.0	3576.58	1.28	7.45
03	1.2	3235.97	1.29	6.8

Table15. Effect of Organic Composition of Mobile Phase -impurity D

S. No	Differ in Organic Composition in the MP	SST outcomes	
		Plate Count	Peak Tailing
01	10%Less	3611.78	1.49
02	**Actual	3686.57	1.42
03	10%More	4866.39	1.50

Table16. Effect of Organic Composition of Mobile Phase-Empa sugar dimer impurity

S. No	Differ in Organic Composition in the MP	SST outcomes		
		Plate Count	Peak Tailing	Resolution
1	10% less	3340.79	1.29	7.9
2	*Actual	3576.58	1.28	7.45
3	10% more	3962.20	0.91	6.3

Conclusion

A stability-indicating UPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Empagliflozin, Metformin, and their impurities. The method showed acceptable retention times (3.293 and 3.962 min) with excellent linearity ($r^2 = 0.999$), accuracy (99.51–102.62%), and precision (%RSD < 2). LOD and LOQ values confirmed adequate sensitivity, while robustness was established through variations in flow rate and mobile phase composition. Forced degradation studies under acid, base, thermal, and oxidative conditions demonstrated specificity and stability-indicating capability. Overall, the method is accurate, precise, robust, and suitable for routine quality control and stability studies.

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